

Overview of Topology Control Algorithm in Mobile Ad hoc Network

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Abstract – Due to its potential applications in various situations such emergency relief, battlefield, environment monitoring and so on, mobile ad hoc network have recently emerged as a research field. The nodes in mobile ad hoc network are spread over a geographical area. These nodes are able to perform processing as well as communicating with each other. These nodes have limited resources and dynamics in their environments thereby the topology control becomes very difficult in MANET. Unlike the fixed network topology of wired networks, each node in MANET can potentially change the network topology by adjusting its transmission range and/or selecting specific nodes to forward its messages thus controlling its set of neighbors. The primary goal of topology control in MANET is to maintain network connectivity and optimization network lifetime and throughput. In this paper, we present an overview of topology control algorithm and various techniques used for topology control

Keywords: Topology control algorithm, Interference, Delay constraint, MANET.

I. Introduction

An ad hoc network consisting of mobile nodes needs a growing requirement of quality of service (QoS) that deals with power source – a weak battery or a small solar cell. Since the energy is the limiting factor for the lifetime and operability of an ad hoc network, many research works are proposed that provides conservative energy. These proposed algorithms in the literature are based on topology control because ad hoc network spends more energy in determining the topology control. Topology control is to dynamically change the nodes transmission range in order to maintain connectivity of the communication graph. The currently best proposals for topology control feature an impressive list of properties. However, these algorithms also often require many unrealistic assumptions. First most algorithms assume that all the nodes know their exact positions, by means of a global positioning system (GPS). Next most algorithms assume that the world is flat and without buildings.

But recently developed topology control algorithms take many constraints such as delay, interference in order to meet the requirements of MANET in topology control. These constraints are strictly related to the nodes transmitting range. A good topology control algorithm can provide a better service for routing algorithm and also save energy, increase network capacity and satisfy the QoS requirements.

II. Topology Control Algorithm

The energy consumption between the two ad hoc nodes during their communication grows at least quadratically with their distance. Having one or more

relay nodes between these two ad hoc nodes helps to save energy by adjusting the transmission power of mobile nodes. The primary target of a topology control algorithm is to abandon long distance communication links and instead route a message over several small energy efficient hops. In order to do this, each node in the MANET chooses neighbors that are not linked to too many far away neighbors in order to prevent the ad-hoc network from being partitioned or the routing paths from becoming noncompetitively long. In general there is a trade-off between network connectivity and sparseness. The topology control algorithms are used to maintain network connectivity while reducing energy consumption and improving network capacity. Instead of transmitting with the maximal power, nodes in a wireless multi-hp network collaboratively determine their transmission power and derive the network topology by forming proper neighbor relation wireless nodes to use adequate transmission power, topology control not only saves energy and prolongs network lifetime, but also improves spatial reuse and mitigate the MAC level medium contentions. On the other hand by reducing the number of links in the network, topology control algorithms actually decrease the degree of routing redundancy. As a result, the topology thus derived is more susceptible to node failures/departures. This problem can be mitigated if an adequate level of routing redundancy can be properly figured into topology control.

III. Classification of Topology Control Algorithm

The topology control algorithm is generally classified into two types: 1) Centralized methods 2) Localized methods or Distributed methods. The centralized methods give usually better results but have huge

communication costs. The distributed methods achieve weaker results but use less communication costs. There are significant robustness and scalability advantages to designing protocols using localized algorithms where the mobile nodes interact with other nodes in restricted vicinity but nevertheless collectively achieve a desired global objective. In localized algorithm, a mobile node communicates with other nodes based on neighborhood. Therefore the communication overhead scales well with increase in network size. It shows that the underlying network topology is constructed in a localized manner. The majority of researches on topology control focus only on reducing the power of each node to save energy extend the network lifetime, choosing a suitable topology for routing and reducing the network interference.

III.1. Delay Based TCA

Many of the topology control algorithm mainly focus on the delay to save the energy. QoS routing protocols consider the end-to-end delay as a measure to implement the topology control. In order to reduce the E2E delay in MANET, the transmission power of the a certain node in a path is increased which reduces the number of nodes between the source and destination nodes. The transmission delay may be decreased due to the reduction in hops and the sum of the queuing delay along a path is also decreased because the number of the intermediate nodes is decreased. Thus, increasing the transmission power may reduce the E2E delay. However it may cause more interference to other nearby active receiving nodes, excessive contention to nearby potential sending nodes which may incur more retransmissions. Therefore reducing delay and minimizing interference are two conflicting goals and it is necessary to jointly consider a tradeoff between them.

Most of the algorithms yield a minimally connected topology which is prone to suffer frequent link breakages in a mobile network. Link breakages result in retransmissions and packet loss and deteriorate the network performance. Some recent works have shown that mobility causes incorrect information in terms of link availability. Consequently topology control algorithm may exploit the mobility to reduce the frequency of link breakages. Secondly, the E2E delay is particularly impacted by the mobility of the nodes in a path. In mobile ad hoc networks, it is necessary to consider the delay caused by the mobility of nodes. If a node has a lower mobility, the impact of mobility on delay could be ignored. If a node has a higher mobility, the node may move out of the sender's transmission range quickly so that the link is unstable and prone to break. Once the link breaks, the transmission delay will become infinite.

Draves et al [2] defined the delay as the transmission delay of the packet. But it did not contain the queuing delay. If there are massive packets in the queue waiting

for transmission since a node cannot transmit multiple packets simultaneously, the queuing delay may take a significant portion of the total delay. The delay in [7] contained the queuing delay and the transmission delay. But it did not explicitly consider the effects channel contention. The contention of the channel can cause access delay and collision at Medium Access Control (MAC) Layer. Because of the direct coupling among different layers, the traditional layered design is not sufficient for multi hop wireless networks.

Mammen et al [3] studied the maximal throughput scaling and the corresponding delay scaling in a random mobile network with restricted node mobility and particular mobility restriction does not affect the delay scaling. Zhu et al [4] showed that a high throughput can be achieved at the cost of very high delay in the mobile network and the network with a low delay has a low throughput. Tradeoff between throughput and delay in mobile ad hoc networks is provided by controlling node's mobility.

III.2. Transmission Power Based TCA

Topology control is one of the most important mechanisms in wireless ad hoc and sensor networks. The main purpose of topology control is to dynamically change the nodes transmitting range to provide connectivity for wireless networks while meeting some given requirements, including power consumption, interference, broadcast, QoS, antennas and reliability [17]. Power control and backbone construction are two major research directions about topology control. Power control is a NP hard problem in ad hoc networks. The problem of assignment of transmitting range is the idealized solution of power control.

Zhang et al [1] pointed out that the physical layer affects the MAC and routing decisions by changing its transmission power and rate. The MAC layer can schedule and allocate the wireless channel and eventually determine the available bandwidth and the packet delay which will then affect the link or path selection in the routing layer. The routing layer selects the transmission path for data packets which will change the contention level at the MAC layer and accordingly the parameters at the physical layer. Thus the mutual impact in different layers should be considered and it is necessary to consider all the controls across different layers jointly to optimize the overall performance while meeting the QoS requirements. Therefore cross layer design of congestion control, routing algorithms with QoS guarantees is one of the most challenging topics in wireless networking [15][16]. Here cross layer design does not mean eliminating the advantages of layering. It means keeping some form of separation, while allowing layers to actively interact, appears to be a good compromise for enabling interaction between layers without eliminating the layering principle.

Chou et al [19] proposed a residual hop count estimation based on nodes available bandwidth and then

adjusted the power level of each node by checking the residual hop count. Tang et al [20] studied interference aware topology control and QoS routing in multi channel wireless mesh networks, they computed the channel assignment for the nodes by going through the edges in a K-Connected sub graph of the network in a non-increasing order of link potential interference values to make the topology interference minimum and then seek routes for QoS connection requests with bandwidth requirements. The transmission power of a node is fixed. Additionally the impact of mobility on the topology control algorithm and delay should be investigated.

Burri et al [8] removed unreliable and redundant links from the network while guaranteeing the connectivity of the network. However the mobility factor was not considered. In practice, the quality between neighboring nodes fluctuates significantly over time especially when the nodes are mobile. Some topology control algorithms with consideration of mobility were also presented [14]. OTTC (one-and-two-hop topology control algorithm) was proposed on the basis of [8]. The nodes compute their transmission radius on the basis of their one-and two-hop neighbors information. Each node orders its one-hop neighbors in an ordered list and then the ordered list are exchanged between the neighbors as [8]. In OTTC the nodes are stationary and AOTTC considers the mobility. However, the reorganization phase in [8] or [14] is applied in response to neighbor changes. The neighbor's changing takes large amount of overhead. Study has been shown that mobility causes incorrect information in terms of link availability and view consistency [14]. Delay is also affected by mobility of a node. Delay has been studied under different mobility models [3][4].

III.3. Interference Based TCA

In addition, the mobility imposes a great impact on the interference based topology control algorithm and the E2E delay. Firstly we need an appropriate interference based topology control algorithm for mobile ad hoc networks. The vast majority of researches on topology control focus only on reducing the power of each node to save energy and reducing the network interference. We need to minimize the interference during topology controls [9][11]. Interference based topology control can combine existing power control with backbone construction preferably. Burkhart et al [9] contradicted the idea with establishing a simple model of interference and proved that a great many former topology control algorithms were not low interference with the definition. They also showed that all the neighbors can interfere with the communication node and defined the number of all neighbors covered by the range of the two communicating nodes as the interference of the path. After that the study of topology control [8][10][11][14] in recent year starts to regard interference control as another objective of topology control, instead of implicitly lower the interference. Previous topology control algorithms [8-14] have only focused on the interference constraint. It is also

important for a topology control algorithm to meet the QoS requirement. Some researches have been carried out in this field.

III.4. Energy Efficient QoS TCA

Jia et al [18] focused on the problem of energy efficient QoS topology control. They proposed an algorithm to find the network topology that all traffics can be routed and the maximal node power is minimized by incrementing node power to connect two nodes that have the shortest Euclidean distance among the unconnected node pairs and then checking if the traffics can be routed on the topology constructed. QoS requirements included bandwidth and delay. However, the traffic demand assumed to be known in prior, interference and node mobility are not taken into account which are important factors that affect the network performance in MANETs.

Xue et al [15] proposed an algorithm to achieve guaranteed throughput while satisfying QoS requirements and guaranteeing that all actual queue backlogs are deterministically upper bounded. Li et al [16] proposed a queuing architecture to exploit the new degree of freedom of choosing service discipline for different arrival process. However, in MANETs, applications may have traffic to be sent at anytime. It is hard to know this information in prior. Moreover, different paths chosen by routing strategy will lead to different end-to-end delay. Since the topology is the foundation of routing, it offers certain paths to be selected by a routing protocol. Thus a good topology control may greatly help the routing protocol to select an appropriate path to meet the E2E delay requirement.

IV. Conclusion

The objective of the topology control algorithm is to adjust the transmission power to minimize interference which is contradictory to the requirement of delay constraint. When transmission power is increased to reduce the delay, which increases the number of neighbors covered by the transmission range and causes more interference from other active nodes in the network. Therefore we make a tradeoff between reducing delay and minimizing interference. By balancing the influence of delay and interference through adjusting the transmission power of nodes, topology is controlled to satisfy both the delay constraint and interference constraint. Consequently, topology control algorithm may exploit the mobility to reduce the frequency of link breakages. Secondly the E2E delay is particularly impacted by the mobility of the nodes in a path. In mobile ad hoc networks, it is necessary to consider the delay caused by the mobility of nodes. If a node has a lower mobility, the impact of mobility on delay could be ignored.

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